

EFFECT OF SOLVENTS ON PARTICLE STRUCTURE, MORPHOLOGY AND OPTICAL PROPERTIES OF ZINC OXIDE NANOPARTICLES

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ABSTRACT

Nanostructured Zinc oxide Nanoparticles were synthesized by simple and low cost sol-gel process in aqueous medium. Zinc Nitrate, Potassium Hydroxide and Sodium hydroxide were used as precursors. The synthesized particles were further characterized by X Ray Diffraction (XRD), Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Photo Luminescence (PL) and Optical Absorption Spectroscopy. The structure, morphology and optical properties are analyzed. XRD and SEM confirmed the formation of ZnO particles with average crystallite size of 36.89 nm and 21.59 nm obtained from solvents NaOH and KOH. The emission peaks were detected by PL spectrum. The optical absorption spectra of the ZnO nanopowders showed blue-shift in wavelength corresponding to bulk. From the analyses of results, it is very clear that precursors used in the present study have played a vital role in surface morphology, structural and optical properties of ZnO nanoparticles.

KEYWORDS:

ZnO nanoparticles, UV-Vis optical absorption, SEM, X Ray Diffraction.

1 .INTRODUCTION

Nanotechnology is a field of science and technology of controlling matter on a scale between 1-100 nanometers. It is a highly multidisciplinary field, bringing together many fields, including electrical and mechanical engineering, physics, chemistry, and biosciences. In fact, one nanometer (nm) is one billionth of a meter, tens of thousands times smaller than the width of a human hair. Nanomaterials have been important in the materials field for a long time due to their unusual mechanical, electrical, optical and magnetic properties. Semiconductor nanoparticles (NPs) are a very important topic in the ongoing research activity across the world. During the past decade a considerable effort has been spent in the preparation and investigation of the family of II-VI nanoscale semiconductors as they exhibit size-dependant properties like scaling of the energy gap and corresponding change in the optical properties.

Among all the II-VI compounds, Zinc oxide (ZnO) is attracting tremendous attention due to its interesting properties like wide direct band gap of 3.3eV at room temperature and high exciton binding energy of 60meV (Shriwas Ashtaputre et al., 2005) .ZnO is widely used in a number of applications like varistors (Rana et al., 2010) UV lasers, gas sensors, photo printing,

electrochemical nanodevice, sunscreen lotion cosmetics and medicated creams (Ravichandrika, et al 2012) due to its several properties such as good transparency, high electron mobility, strong room temperature luminescence. Different types of techniques have been used to synthesize ZnO such as sputtering, spray pyrolysis (Abdelkader Djelloul et al., 2008) Solvothermal (Wang et al., 2005) Hydrothermal (Ni YH et al., 2005), Ball milling method (Lemine et al., 2010) and Wet Chemical method (Satyarana et al 2012; Shah and Alshahry, 2009; Singh et al, 2012). Sol-gel method was reported as one of the well known procedures for the deposition of metal oxide nanoparticles due to its many advantages of being non vacuum, low substrate temperature deposition and low cost.

In the present study ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized by a sol-gel technique from Zinc Nitrate, Potassium Hydroxide and Sodium Hydroxide in aqueous medium. The structure, morphology and optical properties of ZnO were investigated by XRD, SEM, UV-VIS and PL measurements.

2. EXPERIMENT DETAILS

2.1 Materials

Zinc Nitrate, Sodium Hydroxide (NaOH), Potassium Hydroxide (KOH) were purchased and used without further purification.

2.2 Synthesis of Zinc Oxide Nanoparticles

The zinc oxide (ZnO) nanoparticles were prepared by sol-gel method using zinc nitrate and sodium hydroxide as precursors. In this experiment Zinc nitrate (0.4 mol), was dissolved in the distilled water. Then the solution was kept under constant stirring using magnetic stirrer to completely dissolve the zinc nitrate for one hour. After complete dissolution of zinc nitrate, 0.8 mol of sodium hydroxide solution was added under constant stirring, drop by drop touching the walls of the vessel. The reaction was allowed to proceed for 2 h after complete addition of sodium hydroxide. After the completion of reaction, the solution was allowed to settle for overnight and the supernatant solution was then discarded carefully. The remaining solution was centrifuged for 10 min and the supernatant was discarded. Thus obtained nanoparticles were washed three times using distilled water. Washing was carried out to remove the byproducts that were bound with the nanoparticles. After washing, the nanoparticles were dried in micro oven at a maximum temperature of 70°C for several hours. During drying, complete conversion of zinc hydroxide in to zinc oxide takes place.

In a similar manner, ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized from zinc nitrate with potassium hydroxide. Further, the two samples of ZnO nanoparticles were characterized by for their optical and nano-structural properties using X-ray diffraction, scanning electron microscopy, UV-vis optical absorption and Photoluminescence spectra.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 X Ray Diffraction

ZnO structures with different grain sizes can be obtained by using different precursors. Fig1.1 and 1.2 represent the X-ray diffraction patterns of ZnO nanoparticles prepared with different precursors NaOH and KOH. From the patterns it is evident that a definite line broadening of the XRD peaks indicate nano level range of particles in the the prepared material. From XRD patterns analyses, we determined peak intensity, position and width, full-width at half-maximum

(FWHM) data. In Fig 1.1 the diffraction peaks are 31.940° , 34.612° , 36.433° , 47.692° , 56.736° , 62.987° , 66.51° , 68.055° , 69.116° , 72.656° , 77.02° , 81.41° and 89.667° correspond to lattice planes (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103), (200), (112), (201), (004), (202), (104) respectively. In the Fig 1.2 the diffraction peaks are at 31.946° , 34.631° , 36.448° , 47.755° , 56.769° , 62.928° , 66.45° , 68.09° , 69.19° , 77.17° and 81.56° correspond to lattice planes (100), (002), (101), (102), (110), (103), (200), (112), (201), (004), (202), (104) respectively.

Figure: 2.1

Figure: 2.2

Figure 1.1: XRD Spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles synthesized using NaOH. Figure 1.1: XRD Spectrum of ZnO nanoparticles synthesized using KOH,

The diffraction peaks can be indexed for wurtzite type hexagonal structure of ZnO. No peaks from other phase of ZnO or impurities are observed suggesting that high-purity ZnO phase was obtained. From the diffraction patterns it is confirmed that the plane (101) is more intense than

other peaks. The average crystalline size of the particles is calculated using Debye Scherer formula,

$$d_{avg} = 0.9\lambda / \beta \text{ Cos}\theta.$$

Where

- d_{avg} = Average crystalline size
- λ = Wavelength of incident beam (1.5406Å),
- β = FWHM in radians,
- θ = Scattering angle in degree

The average crystallite size of the samples is found to be 36.89 nm in the case of ZnO with NaOH while in the case of ZnO with KOH is 21.59 nm. The XRD pattern for ZnO nanoparticles obtained with water medium with solvents NaOH and KOH shows much sharper peaks. This shows the crystallinity is more synthesized ZnO nanopowders.

3.2 Scanning Electron Microscopy

The morphology and size of the synthesized ZnO particles were studied by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Fig 2.1 and Fig 2.2 represent the effect of solvents (NaOH or KOH) on particle morphology of ZnO Nanopowders observed at different magnifications. These pictures confirm the formation of ZnO nanoparticles SEM micrographs of ZnO nano powders prepared with NaOH ,KOH found to have an irregular spherical shape (whose size in the range of nanometers) along with narrow particle size distribution. It is also observed that most of the particles exhibit some faceting. The estimated particle size from SEM pictures found to be varying between 17nm and 25 nm for the sample synthesized with KOH 30-50nm for the sample synthesized from NaOH. The morphology observed in the samples show fine grains of ZnO converted in to particles when observed at different magnifications. Influence of KOH tends to cause the particle size to decrease, which can be attributed to the decrease in solubility.

Figure: 2.1

Figure: 2.2

Fig 2.1: SEM images of sample at different magnifications obtained using solvent NaOH **Fig 2.2:** SEM images of the sample at different magnifications obtained using solvent KOH.

3.3 UV-Visible Absorption Spectra

Absorption spectroscopy is a powerful non-destructive technique for exploring the optical properties of semiconducting nanoparticles. The optical study was performed to evaluate the potentially useful optical qualities of the NPs. Fig 3.1 and Fig 3.2 represent UV-Vis absorption spectra of ZnO nanoparticles synthesized using NaOH and KOH respectively. From the spectra, it is very clear that both the samples exhibit strong absorption band with maxima around 345-400 nm and another excitonic absorption band located in the range 200-250 nm

Figure 3.1

Figure 3.2

Fig3.1: Optical absorption Spectra of ZnO NPs synthesized using NaOH **Fig3.2:** Optical absorption Spectra of ZnO NPs synthesized using KOH

The value of optical band gap (E_g) has been estimated by fitting the rising end and plateau of the absorption spectra to the sigmoidal formula developed by O' Donnell and coworkers. The band gap corresponding to strong absorption is given by 0.95 eV. Which is higher than bulk ZnO material. The blue shift in the excitonic absorption clearly indicates the quantum confinement property of NPs. It can be seen from the spectra that solvents used do not have any considerable impact on the position of strong absorption band so that size of the particle. But there is very small shift in the absorbance maximum with the use of precursors in order NaOH, KOH. The shift might be associated with the broader nanoparticle distribution such that broader exciton absorbance.

3.4 Photoluminescence Spectra

Photoluminescence is a powerful tool for providing essential information about the physical properties of materials at molecular levels, including shallow and deep level defects and band gap state for energy level. Fig 3.1 and fig 3.2 represent the PL Spectra of ZnO NPs synthesized using NaOH and KOH respectively. The PL spectra in both the samples exhibit two emission peaks, one is located at around 550 nm corresponds to the near band gap excitonic emission and the other is located at around 600 nm. Both the samples showed the prominent peak around 600nm corresponds to the blue green emission. These emissions were found to be extremely broad and this broadening may be due to phonon assisted by transition. As observed in UV-visible optical absorption spectra, there is no significant change in the position of both the emission peaks. Due to broader distribution of nanoparticles in NaOH, the intensity and full-width at half-maximum (FWHM) are found to be small in comparison with the ZnO nanoparticles in the presence of KOH.

Figure 3.1

Figure 3.2

Fig 3.1: PL spectra of ZnO NPs synthesized using NaOH **Fig 3.2:** PL spectra of ZnO NPs synthesized using KOH

CONCLUSION

ZnO nanoparticles were synthesized using simple and cost effective sol-gel process in the presence of NaOH and KOH in aqueous medium. The effect of solvents on structure, morphology and optical properties of ZnO nanopowders were analyzed using XRD, SEM, Optical absorption and Photo Luminescence. The XRD analysis demonstrates that the nanoparticles have the hexagonal wurtzite structure. SEM confirms the morphology and size of the nanoparticles. The decrease in the particle size is observed due to the influence of KOH. Both the samples exhibit bands in the same range but samples with NaOH found to exhibit broader distribution both the samples showed the prominent peak around 600nm corresponds to the blue green emission of PL spectra. The sol-gel route employed in this work is simple, cost effective and free of pollution and therefore, the technique can be extended to prepare many other important semiconducting metal oxide nanoparticles. These ZnO nanoparticles can be used in different industrial applications viz., luminescent material for fluorescent tubes, active medium for lasers, sensors etc. From the

analyses of results, it is very clear that precursors used in the present study have played a vital role in surface morphology, structural and optical properties of ZnO nanoparticles.

References

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